

Benefits of using Digital Technologies in Education in Geology Classes

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Abstract: *The relevance of the chosen topic is associated with the need to rationally organize the educational process, to ensure the use of different information systems, to pay more attention to the activity of students in the lesson, to develop critical thinking..*

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Today, creating the digital industry of the future requires launching the digital transformation of the country by increasing the level of human capital development, rapid digital transformation in education. Today's classrooms are vastly different from those of a decade ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, iPads, tablets, smartboards, and other types of educational technology. Researchers admit that no one area can be more important than education for the development of the state.

The concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 provides for the implementation of several activities for the introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the education process [1]. In particular, the individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, the development of distance education services, the widespread introduction of webinar, online, blended learning and flipped classroom technologies[2] were discussed.

It is known that "blended learning", "flipped classroom" technologies are forms of organization of the educational process, which include aspects that form the student's skills and competencies for creative and systematic thinking, independent decision-making, organization of scientific activities. At the same time, these forms of training are based on independent education, which form the skills of self-organization, the ability to constantly continue in development, clearly set goals, perspective.

As elsewhere in the world, Uzbekistan has seen the emergence of a seven-screen generation of digital generation - TVs, computers, tablets, phablets, smartphones and smartwatches. As a result of having such a dense digital environment and constant interaction with it, the thinking and information processing processes of today's students are fundamentally different from previous thought and information processes. The digital generation cannot and should not be taught in the same way that our parents learned. In the training of this generation, blackboard and white chalk will not be used. [3]

Changing blackboard to white and chalk to marker doesn't change anything, which means it can't be a way to encourage modern students to gain knowledge and develop skills to succeed in the labor

market. Currently, digital technology has swept the world and people are making changes in all areas of their lives. Their appearance empowered students and faculty.

The use of digital technology saves time in the classroom when explaining new material, inspires teachers to explore new teaching methods and approaches, increases motivation to learn, and as a result, the quality of teaching activity and knowledge increases. Geography plays an important role in the formation of the scientific worldview. It gives a holistic view of the world and forms a common culture. [4]

Geography teaches how to combine information from multiple sources and use a geographic map for communication.

Geography has a wide range of tools for stimulating students' learning and cognitive activity: the content of academic subjects, the use of various teaching tools, active forms and methods, integration and strengthening of the practical orientation of the school with other subjects. A person receives a lot of information 89% by sight, about 10% by hearing. Non-standard lessons are a great opportunity to learn topics with the help of visualizations: work with computer tasks such as presentations, interactive maps, online tests, syllabi.

Conducting non-standard classes requires the use of unusual structures that differ as much as possible from traditional forms of organizing geography lessons for educational activities.

They add more variety, increase interest, help improve the educational process. To successfully develop absolutely any activity, including education, we need the cognitive interest we get in non-standard classes.

Digital technology can be used at any stage of the classroom, to learn new material, to check homework, to reinforce and summarize topics. [5]

The use of digital technologies in geography lessons will help to: - improve the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process; -Increasing interest in education -Activation of students' cognitive sphere - control over teaching and learning outcomes;

For fun exercises and assignments in the classroom, you can use the LearningApps.org program, which allows you to quickly and most importantly, accurately, create geography assignments on a variety of topics in a playful way. The e-learning materials can be used with an interactive whiteboard or as individual exercises for students.

Students complete tasks with interest: they find a pair, make chronological lines, fill in the gaps in the text, make crossword puzzles, geographic races, find a puzzle, and so on.

This program is very convenient to use to check the nomenclature in grades 7-11. Consider the example of nomenclature for Class 9 when one student is working with a map on a whiteboard and the other student is working with a nomenclature on a computer.

The administrative-territorial structure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where in the program we can include separately the Republic of Uzbekistan, the regions and the republics. The screen presents a map and flags on specific objects, and the children's task is to correctly match the flag and the name of the object.

If a student has made a mistake, the program will highlight that mistake with a red color, and there is an opportunity to think and correct it, so that the teacher can work with groups of students, create quick exercises in class, mark homework, receive hyperlinks from students. Checking the completion of the task, the introduction of new information and communication technologies into the educational process will help to prepare students with the highest quality.

The use of multimedia in the learning process in any subject is an attempt to introduce intensity into the educational process, optimize it, motivate students to study any subject, implement developing educational ideas, as well as offer one of the ways to improve educational abilities. Increase the pace of lessons, independent work .

Information and communication technologies contribute to the development of logical thinking, culture of mental work, the formation of students' skills of independent work, and also have a significant impact on the motivational sphere of the educational process.

Broadening the scope of ICT inclusion in higher education in general is a requirement of the time. Experts from all over the world admit that in the future, the need for IT specialists will only grow. In his address to the Oliy Majlis of January 24, 2020, the head of state put forward a proposal to implement the project —One million programmers. Therefore, we, too, should be disconnected from world development, despite existing shortcomings and obstacles, to strive to train highly demanded skilled personnel through the introduction of ICT. [6]

Based on the foregoing, we propose the following: – to take steps in the way of education and professional learning, to ensure that the country does not lag behind technogenic achievements, it is necessary to massively develop competencies in the use of information and communication technologies among all citizens of our country; – It is necessary to have at least one laptop for every family in the country.

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